

**PATRIOTISM AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN INVOLVING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE
ARMED FORCES**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6712340>

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Annotation : *This in the article young people armed forces to the system attractive make them . mudofa Ministry in the system studies zeal and patriotism feeling formation and development about statement given.*

The key words : *homeland , patriotism , motherland , defense , service .*

Growing up coming young generation Armed Forces to the system attractive first of all in schools , education education in the process to the body is coming .

To all of us good known patriotism each state of life spiritual basis is calculated and community har two-sided development about eng important mobilization seeker power as show will be . Therefore for each young generation own effect transfer trying to us lying down harmful effects against solid immunity formation and Our homeland destiny for responsibility feeling strengthen measures instead increased is coming .

That's it complex in case army sifida courage and matonat , Vatanga loyalty with service to do school past navqiron young people reliable base and support as service does . In this regard young people Armed Forces to the system attractive in reaching patriotism upbringing to us hand is coming .

Current period jadal step forward . putting a at the time person potential , spiritual-intellectual factor development ustuvor importance focus current matter became . Of our homeland stable development for there is intellectual potential effective to work hit , experts own maintenance conscious approach their formation . personal responsibility and initiative qualities strengthen big importance has . Human personal responsibility , initiative and devotion qualities esa Homeland chindildan out of love , out of patriotism power takes . That's it boisdan Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev 's " Har how state policy basis patriotism upbringing organized " . . words in the background deep meanings is embodied . Of patriotism moving power esa of

people spiritual world , intellectual potential , book mutolaasi their in life How important place hold with measured . Therefore for our President book mutolaasini development issue state policy level raised , even military in parts also in soldiers to the book which was heat up increases . Of our great ancestors ezgu ideas , teachings , writings based on education and education radical reforms in the field high stage take exit , the future of the country for responsibility own assume take able which was new generation adult delivery on work consistent to be continued reach need always scream is coming .

That's it factors come out without state and society development moving power which was patriotism factor solid relied on without the work take to go da'vat reaches . Homeland to love is one's own family , neighborhood , profession , territory and Uzbekistan in appreciation show in the presence of separately attention focus should .

To our youth first of all ourselves all in the field - to the Motherland , to the people faithful being , to the loop , to the profession mehr putting , parents , society in front of our duty in earnest . practical sample to be need .

a young age patriotism upbringing wide scale instead increase if we patriotism omili state and society scale instead increasing spiritual policy moving force becomes .

In 2017-2021 Uzbekistan Of the Republic development five ustuvor direction on actions strategy confirmed to him according to fifth ustuvor Security as a direction , international harmony and religious tolerance supply and deep thoughtful reciprocal beneficial and practical external policy in the field ustuvor direction scope incoming Uzbekistan Republic Armed Of their forces warrior power and potential increase with a in a row young people patriotism in the spirit upbringing on measure measures are also in place being increased .

Ministers to the decision of the court No. 140 of February 23, 2018 building young people military-patriotic in the spirit upbringing concept functional was released .

This in conception young people military-patriotic in the spirit upbringing issue physically and spiritual healthy generation to educate oid integral education education of the system organic and inseparable part as Uzbekistan . . Republic in 2017-2021 development on Actions strategy requirements based on national and in the world advanced experiments , today Uzbekistan real socio-political in life phase with compatible as improvement issue separately attention is focused .

Young people military patriotism in the spirit of upbringing purpose at a young age of society different networks , especially the military field with in contact which was state service species activity show , calm down and military conditions Constitution and military duty faithful to be in them own home and people destiny for high responsibility and responsibility such as important properties formation consists of .

State young people military-patriotic in the spirit upbringing system organized his . . results monitoring keep provider social institutes is calculated . State young of the generation education process in the family , preschool education , general middle education , profession education and higher education institutions within organized reaches .

Military-patriotic youth in the spirit upbringing works following four stage instead will be increased :

a) First stage (3-7 years old) surrounding olam , Vatan about first imaginations appear to be stage in which . family and preschool in educational institutions to children different poems , melody and songs teaching , cartoon and different games organized make pictures . draw through the world consciousness , state with magnifiers (flag , coat of arms , anthem) to get acquainted sauce them she swallow love to form own into takes . This stage to the following basic attention focuses on :

military-patriotic in the direction of first cross section formation in order to fairy tale and stories telling to give ;

of children imagination to expand doir pictures draw and physical ability strengthen for different competition and choices organized that is . through them spiritual incentives ;

military museums and military patriotism subject with depending on culture and rest gardens excursions to organize ;

b) The second students at the stage (7-16 years) Homeland love and loyalty strengthening , in front of the motherland childhood duty high responsibility with do in them Armed To our strength which was positive ideas more expansion , military service nufuzini upgrade , youth physically healthy , spiritual mature , wide world dependent , independent thought angles competent man in quality formation such as ezgu to work are given .

At this stage :

modern heroes about articles , fiction publications mutolaa to do ;

general middle education in institutions military patriotism in the direction of cultural and educational activities , thematic nights and song choices organized from performances . sheets show to do ;

reader young people with the participation of “ Our Motherland eye like our pupil We will save ”, “ The fate of the country my my destiny ” essays selection organized to reach ;

“ Mard boy ” state award worth which was our compatriots with meetings transfer , they achieved win and results young people in the middle wide propaganda work take to go

General middle education schools high class students with the participation of “ Temurbek Heirs ” military- sports games step by step organized to reach separately importance to give ;

Conclusion so he said this Concept young people in the middle military patriotism upbringing efficiency increase , in them high spiritual and moral qualities , citizenship position , homeland love and uni eye pupil to keep focused knowledge and skills increase for methodical basis as service does .

Young people Armed Forces to the system attractive in reaching this ustuvor direction and military-patriotic in the spirit upbringing concept big importance profession reaches .